

VULNERABILITY TO VIABILITY
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Co-Producing Resilient Pathways from Vulnerability to Viability for Small-Scale Crab Fishers in the Indian Sundarbans

V2V Working Paper No. 2026-04

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January 2026

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Publication design and formatting:

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School of Environment, Enterprise and Development, Faculty of Environment, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada

How to cite:

Das, B. K., Paul, L., Bhattacharya, S., Parida, P. K., Johnson, C., Debroy, P., Bera, S., Kumari, S., Karnatak, G., Ganguly, S., Jha, D., Chakraborty, A., Gogoi, P., Thangjam, N., & Ramteke, M. (2026). *Co-producing resilient pathways from vulnerability to viability for small-scale crab fishers in the Indian Sundarbans*. V2V Working Paper 2026-04. V2V Global Partnership, University of Waterloo, Canada. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19358335>

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V2V Global Partnership is supported by the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada under its Partnership Grant Program.

Social Sciences and Humanities
Research Council of Canada

Conseil de recherches en
sciences humaines du Canada

Canada

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Table of Contents

Abstract.....	1
1. Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background and context	1
1.2 Learning area	2
1.3 Socio-economic profile of Sundarbans’ fishers	2
1.4 Power relations and stakeholder conflicts.....	3
1.5 Ecosystem degradation, justice, and livelihoods.....	3
1.6 Contribution of small-scale fisheries to India	3
1.7 Crab fishers’ profile and BLC rights.....	4
2. Theoretical and conceptual framework.....	4
2.1 Co-production concepts	4
2.2 Problems addressed.....	5
2.3 Area of approach.....	5
2.4 Rationale for the approach	5
3. Data collection	5
3.1 Participant selection and composition.....	6
3.2 Procedure applied.....	6
3.3 Data analysis	7
3.4 Validation and triangulation.....	7
3.5 Ethical considerations	7
3.6 Limitations and reflexivity.....	7
4. Key findings and discussions.....	7
5. Co-produced solutions	14
6. Collaborative implementation and monitoring for the mud crab fishery.....	15
7. Executive summary.....	17
8. Conclusions.....	19
References.....	20

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Abstract

Small-scale mud crab fisheries are a critical livelihood for marginalised, mangrove-dependent communities in the Indian Sundarbans. This study examines how vulnerability can be transformed into viability through a co-production approach that integrates fisher knowledge, stakeholder perspectives, and applied research. Using a structured, participatory multi-stakeholder workshop involving crab fishers, traders, women's groups, local institutions, and researchers, the study identifies key drivers shaping the mud crab fishery and collaboratively develops pathways for resilience and sustainability. Findings reveal that climate-induced hazards, habitat degradation, inequitable market structures, debt dependency, and restrictive governance regimes constitute major sources of vulnerability. The analysis demonstrates that vulnerability and viability are not opposing states, but co-existing conditions shaped by power relations, access, and adaptive capacity. Co-produced solutions prioritised by stakeholders include spawning-season protection, community-based monitoring, collective marketing and cold storage, women-led enterprises, mangrove restoration, and inclusive co-management reforms. The study offers policy-relevant insights for advancing equitable, climate-resilient fisheries management in the Sundarbans and comparable deltaic socio-ecological systems globally.

Keywords Small-scale fisheries • Mud crab fishery • Vulnerability to viability • Co-production • Climate resilience • Indian Sundarbans

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and context

The Sundarbans is a dynamic and diverse socio-ecological system where people, tigers, fisheries, agriculture and related activities, including tourism, coexist. The system is highly complex and interconnected, linking every aspect of life, from climatic harshness and drinking water scarcity to the struggle for basic needs. However, the rich aquatic resources continue to sustain local communities, enabling them to endure and thrive amid persistent challenges and risks. It is the world's largest contiguous mangrove delta, with 40 % lying in West Bengal and 60 % in Bangladesh (Giri, 2007). It supports thirty true mangrove species and hundreds of fish and bird species. Nearly 7.5 million people depend on its ecosystem, with small-scale fisheries (SSF) providing a significant livelihood base (Islam et al., 2022). In the Indian Sundarbans, around 40,000 households rely solely on mangrove-based fishing (Pattanaik, 2021).

The estuarine mix of freshwater and seawater creates ideal conditions for spawning and nursery habitats. Among its resources, mud crabs are the most valuable, sustaining a vibrant small-scale fishery. However, crab-collecting communities face persistent vulnerabilities due to environmental hazards, inequitable market structures, and weak governance (Nayak et al., 2014). Around 34 % of the population lives below the poverty line, and nearly half face food insecurity (Das and Hazra, 2020). Recurrent cyclones, tidal surges, and land erosion intensify livelihood instability, driving diversification and migration (Das and Hazra, 2020; Mondal et al., 2023).

Mud crabs (*Scylla* spp.), locally known as “mud crabs” or “black crabs”, are a vital component of the Indian Sundarbans fisheries, providing crucial cash income for coastal and estuarine households, particularly landless and marginal fishers (Basu & Bhattacharjee, 2024; Molla et al., 2009). The fishery, dominated by *S. olivacea* and *S. serrata*, depends on wild harvests from mangrove creeks and intertidal mudflats, supplying live crabs to domestic and export markets. Crab harvesting, fattening, and marketing offer continuous livelihood opportunities, with women’s participation in fattening and value addition contributing significantly to income diversification and empowerment (Hasanuzzaman et al., 2014; Das and Mandal, 2016). Collection involves traps, baited lines, gillnets, and hand excavation, and crabs move through multi-tiered trade networks that shape prices and fisher earnings (Dana et al., 2015). Despite their economic importance, mud crab stocks face mounting threats from overexploitation, juvenile capture, mangrove degradation, and climate-induced stresses such as salinity rise and cyclones (Pati et al., 2023). Recent initiatives, community crab pens, hatcheries, women-led enterprises, and participatory monitoring, reflect growing adaptive responses (Pati et al., 2023). However, critical knowledge gaps in stock assessment, value chain dynamics, and climate impacts necessitate integrated, co-produced research and management by institutions such as Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute and National Mission for Clean Ganga (Anon, 2024).

Mud crabs hold strong market potential. Bangladesh’s Sundarbans exported US\$35–42 million worth of crabs in 2019–20, indicating robust demand in Southeast Asia (Parvin, 2023; ICSF, 2025). In comparison, India’s crab exports were valued at US\$19.4 million in 2000, of which mud crabs contributed US\$5.5 million (Iyer, 2017). Despite high prices, profits remain concentrated among traders and exporters, leaving primary collectors with minimal returns.

1.2 Learning area

The Sundarbans function as a complex social-ecological system (SES) where mangroves and human livelihoods are interdependent. The mangrove–estuarine interface supports fisheries, yet this equilibrium is increasingly fragile. Over the last few decades, about 35% of mangrove cover has been lost due to cyclones and to the conversion of wetlands for aquaculture and agriculture (Rahman et al., 2025). Unregulated trawling, salinity intrusion, and recurrent disasters have contributed to habitat degradation and “multidimensional vulnerabilities” (Rahman et al., 2025; Das and Hazra, 2020).

Crab fishing is low-capital, dependent on traditional gear such as traps and lines, and closely tied to local ecological knowledge. It often complements finfish capture and honey collection, reflecting the multi-use character of the landscape (Danda et al., 2017). However, ecological stressors such as habitat loss and pollution, combined with poverty and weak institutional support, are eroding the fishery’s resilience (Danda et al., 2017).

1.3 Socio-economic profile of Sundarbans’ fishers

Small-scale fishers in the Sundarbans remain among India’s most marginalised groups. Many belong to landless or low-caste households with limited education. A 2015 survey covering 300 households across

six blocks of the Sundarbans reported that most families had annual incomes between ₹50,000 and ₹100,000 (approximately US\$700–1,400). A significant portion, however, earned as little as ₹20,000 to ₹30,000 annually, an amount far below subsistence levels (Ghosh et al., 2016). Multiple occupations are common, with agriculture as the primary source and fishing as secondary (Ghosh et al., 2016). Assets are modest, comprising small ponds, simple gear, and minimal savings. Access to safety nets and credit remains limited, and poverty is most acute in mangrove-adjacent areas exposed to frequent cyclones and salinity (Das and Hazra, 2020).

Mud crab fishers are particularly vulnerable. Many are landless and dependent on credit from middlemen, creating debt traps. They face high occupational risks, wildlife attacks, piracy, and tidal hazards, yet earn a fraction of market value due to a trader-dominated supply chain. The lack of infrastructure, such as cold storage and transport facilities, adds to their economic fragility (Yadava, 2003). Declining catches, rising costs, and limited alternatives deepen cycles of debt and marginalisation (Yadava, 2003).

1.4 Power relations and stakeholder conflicts

Overlapping jurisdictions and unequal power mark fisheries governance in the Sundarbans. The primary tension exists between fishers and the Forest Department, which enforces colonial-era Boat License Certificates (BLCs) (Mistri and Das, 2015). These are often applied arbitrarily, stigmatising fishers as exploiters while ignoring broader drivers like illegal aquaculture and pollution.

Institutional fragmentation further weakens governance. Departments of Forest, Fisheries, and Panchayats operate with little coordination, while top-down conservation approaches conflict with livelihood needs (Mukherjee et al., 2018). In these gaps, informal power brokers, middlemen, moneylenders, and trader syndicates control access and pricing (Chakraborty et al., 2025). Consequently, small-scale fishers remain excluded from decision-making and lack secure rights.

1.5 Ecosystem degradation, justice, and livelihoods

Rapid ecological decline is reshaping the justice and survival of small-scale fishers. Salinisation, embankment breaches, and the expansion of shrimp aquaculture are degrading mangroves, while cyclones repeatedly destroy infrastructure and homes. These shocks force families into debt or migration, with men seeking labour elsewhere and women facing increased burdens (Das and Hazra, 2020).

Despite long-standing customary use, fishers rarely hold land or resource rights. Many face eviction and lack compensation for climate losses, while external investors freely acquire land for aquaculture or tourism. These double standards fuel dispossession and criminalise traditional livelihoods. Reduced fish stocks lengthen fishing trips, worsen poverty, and trigger further migration (Nayak et al., 2014; Das, 2017). The result is a reinforcing cycle: ecological decline deepens poverty, which in turn drives unsustainable practices.

1.6 Contribution of small-scale fisheries to India

Small-scale fisheries contribute 60–70 % of India's fish production and employ over 14 million people, forming the backbone of the sector (FAO, 2003). They rely on modest boats, simple gear, and near-shore operations to supply affordable nutrition to rural and urban markets. Globally, over 90% of SSF catch is consumed locally, and India follows a similar pattern. Although often underreported, high-value species such as mud crabs play a vital role in sustaining regional economies (Bhaumik, 2015).

Women’s contributions in processing and marketing remain undervalued in policy. The sector continues to face challenges of limited credit, weak infrastructure, and competition from mechanised trawlers (Basurto et al., 2025). Despite this, SSFs remain among the most socially and environmentally sustainable pillars of India’s blue economy. Within this, the Sundarbans mud crab fishery represents a niche, low in volume but high in value, and crucial for marginalised coastal livelihoods.

1.7 Crab fishers’ profile and BLC rights

Fishing in the Sundarbans is small-scale and family-based, using wooden boats or dugouts with small engines. Women contribute substantially through post-harvest work and marketing. Most fishers sell locally, earning a modest yet essential income.

Access, however, is restricted by the Forest Department’s BLC system, a colonial legacy that regulates entry into mangrove waters. Few hold licenses directly, forcing many to rent them from brokers at high cost. Even licensed fishers report frequent harassment and confiscation (Mistri and Das, 2015). What should serve as livelihood protection instead of perpetuating insecurity.

Sundarbans fishers remain ecologically rooted but socially constrained, facing fragile ecosystems and inequitable governance that continue to limit both rights and income opportunities.

2. Theoretical and conceptual framework

2.1 Co-production concepts

This experiential work draws on observation and reflective processes akin to journaling to capture and narrate the visible and invisible lived realities of Sundarbans. Through visual documentation and descriptive accounts from community members, we developed a guiding framework of different interconnected themes: identity, power, collectivism, and resources. These themes emerged from our interpretation of images and narratives, offering a lens for understanding how communities in the Sundarbans navigate challenges while sustaining resilience. The mixed style of this work helped triangulate interpretations, allowing the strengths of one method to enhance the other and, ultimately, to provide a more complete and nuanced understanding of the dynamics at play.

Figure 1

Vulnerability to viability framework for crab collection in Sundarbans

2.2 Problems addressed

Small-scale mud crab fisheries in the Indian Sundarbans are a critical source of livelihood for marginalised and landless communities, yet they operate under severe ecological, economic, and governance pressures. The fragile mangrove ecosystem that sustains these fisheries is rapidly degrading due to salinisation, habitat conversion, and recurrent cyclones. At the same time, fishers face economic marginalisation within inequitable value chains and restrictive licensing regimes that favour authorities, traders, and outside investors. Although crabs generate high market value and support thousands of households, frontline fishers bear the highest ecological, economic, and physical risks yet receive the smallest share of benefits. Existing research has often examined ecological change, market dynamics, or governance conflicts in isolation, limiting understanding of how these drivers interact and how local stakeholders perceive pathways to viability. To address this gap, a multistakeholder workshop was held to integrate diverse perspectives and generate actionable insights to support both the sustainability of the resource and the livelihoods of those who depend on it.

2.3 Area of approach

- 1) To identify and prioritise the key drivers of vulnerability affecting small-scale mud crab fishers and traders in the Indian Sundarbans, as perceived by diverse stakeholders.
- 2) To document and evaluate locally proposed solutions that could enhance the viability and sustainability of the crab fishery.
- 3) To synthesise stakeholder insights into an actionable plan that can inform policy decisions, strengthen community initiatives through collaborative implementation and monitoring of the mud crab fishery.

2.4 Rationale for the approach

This study is framed to fill a critical gap by providing an integrated, stakeholder-driven synthesis of vulnerabilities and solutions in the Sundarbans mud crab fishery. The study not only focuses on describing problems but also on co-producing applied outputs, a set of prioritised drivers, and a portfolio of proposed solutions. This approach generates knowledge that is both academically robust and practically relevant. It offers a foundation for adaptive policy, strengthens community voices in resource governance, and establishes a baseline for long-term management of one of the most undervalued yet vital small-scale fisheries in India.

3. Data collection

This study used a participatory consensus as an applied research instrument to co-produce knowledge on drivers of vulnerability and pathways to viability for the small-scale mud-crab fishery in the Indian Sundarbans. Therefore, the workshop adopted a participatory tool that combined structured group facilitation with the Consensus Method (ICA) and elements of the Nominal Group Technique (NGT), enabling participants to move from individual observations to collective synthesis and prioritised actions. The intent was not to produce quantitative modelling, but to convert lived experience and stakeholder judgment into a validated, policy-relevant problem–solution framework.

3.1 Participant selection and composition

Participants were selected to ensure coverage of the fishery value chain and governance arenas. The invited cohort included small-scale fishers and crab collectors (men and women), local traders and depot owners, representatives of women's self-help groups, community-based organisations and NGOs, panchayat members and local fisheries/forest officials, and researchers with regional expertise (n = 19). Selection criteria emphasised (a) direct involvement in crab harvesting or marketing, (b) geographic representation across Sundarbans blocks, and (c) willingness to engage in collective problem solving. The mix aimed to foreground marginal voices (women collectors, landless harvesters) while capturing perspectives of market and governance actors.

3.2 Procedure applied

The one-day workshop followed a five-stage, structured protocol (Figure 2):

Figure 2

Procedure of the data collection workshop

Flip charts, cards, and maps were photographed for record-keeping. Group and plenary discussions were audio-recorded with consent and transcribed. Field notes captured facilitation dynamics and nonverbal cues. Listed items and rankings were entered into a spreadsheet for simple frequency counts and preparation of summary tables and a problem - solution matrix.

3.3 Data analysis

Using a framework approach, transcripts and workshop materials were coded under environmental, economic, social, and institutional themes. Two researchers developed and refined the codebook through independent coding and discussion. Synthesised outputs identified key drivers, causal links, and proposed solutions, supported by participant quotes. Descriptive counts indicated emphasis but were interpreted qualitatively rather than statistically.

3.4 Validation and triangulation

Findings were cross-checked with secondary literature, regional studies, official statistics, and field observations. A summary of results was shared with participants within two weeks for feedback and corrections. Their responses were integrated into the final synthesis, serving as a single-round Delphi-style validation.

3.5 Ethical considerations

Participants provided informed consent for recordings and use of anonymised quotes. Facilitators ensured inclusive participation, particularly for women and marginalised groups. Identifiers were removed, and quotes are presented anonymously by stakeholder type (e.g., “Fisher, Gosaba”).

3.6 Limitations and reflexivity

We recognise that the workshop reflects the views of purposively selected participants and that some voices (e.g., highly marginalised households, women fishers, and absent seasonal migrant fishers) may be under-represented. Prioritisation was achieved through facilitated consensus rather than blind scoring, which persuasive individuals can influence; to mitigate this, we used silent idea generation, small-group clustering, and member checking. Where possible, findings were cross-checked against external data to reduce over-reliance on perception alone. The methodology intentionally favours depth, contextual understanding and practical relevance over statistical generalisation.

4. Key findings and discussions

During the multi-stakeholder workshop, participants distinguished between two broad sets of forces shaping the mud crab fishery: drivers of vulnerability (–) and enablers of viability (+).

On the vulnerability side, fishers and traders pointed to **Drivers of Vulnerability (–)**

“Climate hazards, hydrological alterations, mangrove degradation, rising salinity, embankment breaches, habitat loss, pollution, tourism pressure, fishery displacement, migration, stock depletion, wildlife encounters (tiger, crocodile, snake), health risks, uncertainty of catch, market intermediary pressure, indebtedness, limited livelihood alternatives, fishing exclusion rights (BLC constraints), overharvesting, weak law enforcement, unregulated market, lack of certification (e.g., no MSC for Sundarbans crab; Chilika certified), theft, declining wild seed collection, absence of hatcheries, generational disengagement, low producer share in market returns.”

However, participants also emphasised that fishery remains viable for many households because of a parallel set of enabling conditions. These included:

High tidal exchange and nutrient-rich waters, presence of breeding and nursery grounds, sustained export demand for mud crab, strong base of traditional ecological knowledge, women's active role in collection and marketing, community willingness to adopt better practices, and cultural identity linked to fishing.

“...the reasons we can still fish and continue our business,” as expressed by the stakeholders.

During the workshop process, it became evident that several drivers function both as vulnerabilities and as enabling conditions, depending on context. Many drivers are interlinked, some directly reinforcing others, while others operate indirectly as root causes. To refine the list and strengthen causal understanding, a second round of discussion was facilitated.

In this round, participants:

Discussed which issues could realistically be addressed locally and which required broader state- or national-level engagement.

For example, dam and barrage construction was recognised as a critical driver shaping hydrological change, yet participants acknowledged that altering such infrastructure is politically and technically complex. Instead, they discussed potential ways to bypass or adapt to these structural constraints.

Through this iterative discussion, new factors also emerged and were added to the list. The final consolidated set of drivers of vulnerability and enablers of viability, as drafted by the stakeholders, is presented below (Figure 3).

Figure 3

System map showing vulnerability drivers and viability enablers

a) Environmental drivers

Rising salinity and changing hydrology

Rising salinity and altered hydrological regimes are reshaping the ecological conditions that underpin mud crab populations. *Scylla serrata* exhibits moderate salinity tolerance, with juveniles surviving between 5–40 ppt, but optimal growth and survival occur within 10–20 ppt and around 30°C, where survival reaches 96–98%. Recruitment and larval survival depend on estuarine salinity gradients and periodic freshwater influx, which have been increasingly disrupted by reduced upstream discharge and saline storm surges. Elevated creek salinities beyond 25–30 ppt in the dry months can impair larval transport, limit nursery habitats, and heighten stress during moulting (Ruscoe et al., 2004). Fishers report declining catches in upper estuaries and a shift in crab abundance toward more saline southern creeks, indicating redistribution rather than uniform decline. However, extreme salinity events and prolonged dry spells threaten breeding success and juvenile settlement, undermining long-term fishery viability.

Cyclones, storms, and embankment breaches

Participants ranked recurrent cyclones, notably Amphan (2020) and Yaas (2021), as among the most devastating hazards. Fishers described how storm surges break embankments, flood crab fattening ponds, destroy nets and traps, and capsize small boats. “A single cyclone can take away a whole year’s investment,” said one crab fatter. Workshop facilitators noted that satellite data confirm accelerated sea-level rise (up to +5.2 mm yr⁻¹) and shoreline retreat, corroborating these lived experiences of island inundation and village loss. Several fishers recounted being forced into temporary migration after storms ruined their homes and gear. COVID-19 lockdowns in 2020–2021 compounded these impacts by disrupting markets and supply chains, leaving many families stranded without income or food.

Habitat degradation and pollution

Stakeholders highlighted habitat degradation as a persistent stressor. Crab collectors cited siltation of tidal creeks, destruction of mangrove roots by trawlers, and effluents from shrimp farms that “turn the water black and kill small crabs.” Women noted that plastics and chemical runoff foul nursery grounds and reduce juvenile survival. These accounts align with studies showing that trawling and aquaculture discharges degrade benthic habitats and hinder recruitment of key species.

Declining fish stocks and fishery displacement

Many participants linked environmental changes to shifting fishing practices. With freshwater species declining, households increasingly rely on mud crab as a fallback resource. One fisher observed, “We catch mostly crabs now because the fish are gone.” While crab prices have risen, fishers warned that heavier effort is already reducing average size and catch per unit effort. Wildlife encounters and biological hazards

Wildlife encounters and biological hazards

Fishers voiced growing fears of wildlife hazards, reporting more frequent tiger and crocodile encounters, sometimes fatal. Experts attributed this to mangrove degradation and prey loss, which draws predators closer to fishing zones and settlements.

Seasonal catch practice biology studies

During the peak breeding season, crabs, especially berried females, are heavily harvested, reducing reproductive success and long-term yields (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Seasonality map of crab breeding season and crab harvesting

b) Economic drivers of vulnerability

Economic pressures emerged as a major driver of vulnerability, cutting across nearly all stakeholder groups in the Sundarbans mud crab fishery. Participants described their livelihoods as “hand-to-mouth,” heavily dependent on wild seed collection and volatile market prices. One elderly crab collector summarised: “Even in a good month, we barely survive; the rivers decide our income, not us.”

Low and uncertain incomes

Fishers reported average monthly household earnings of only ₹10,000–12,000 (US\$120–150), barely enough for basic needs. Much of this income goes toward fuel, boat repairs, nets, and bait. As one young harvester explained, “By the time we pay for diesel and repair the engine, there is nothing left to take home.” Even minor shocks, cyclones, engine failures, or price drops can push them into debt. Crab fishing spans roughly nine months a year, with 18 major trips yielding 70–100 kg per trip. Seasonal variations: about four trips during the monsoon, eight in autumn, and six in winter, the most productive season. Daily harvests range from 2 to 10 kg, totalling 230 to 260 kg annually per fisher, yet irregular catch and high costs keep incomes low and uncertain (Sen & Haldar, 2024).

Market dependence and middlemen

Participants repeatedly raised concerns about the traders' and middlemen's monopoly overpricing, due to the absence of cold storage and transport facilities. Catches must be sold immediately to avoid spoilage, forcing fishers to accept whatever price is offered. “We have to sell today or watch our crabs die,” lamented a woman crab grader. “The middlemen know this and cut the price.” Evidence shows that intermediaries capture most of the profits due to poor infrastructure (CIFRI, 2024).

Women involved in grading and processing also face exclusion: “We do the sorting and cleaning, but we do not decide the price,” shared one member of a women’s group. Despite their crucial role, they remain sidelined in market negotiations.

Crab fatteners face additional losses due to high moulting mortality, exacerbated by price fluctuations and increased operating costs. To recover, they often take on higher risks, which only deepens financial strain.

Debt cycles (Dadon System)

Seasonal instability drives reliance on informal loans for inputs like salt, bait, and gear, repaid through future catches. When poor weather or cyclones reduce harvests, fishers return empty-handed but still indebted. “The storm takes the crabs, but we still owe the money,” said one harvester. These recurring debts trap households in a cycle of dependency and prevent investment in better gear or alternative livelihoods.

Limited alternatives and uneven gains

With little or no agricultural land, most families lack fallback options when fishing fails. Some traders acknowledged the unequal distribution of benefits: “The big buyers in Kolkata make money even in a bad season; the collectors always lose.” This underscores widening disparities along the value chain and growing dependence on precarious, migrant-based labour.

c) Institutional drivers of vulnerability

The third major driver of vulnerability discussed during the workshop was institutional and governance barriers that limit access to resources and bargaining power, exposing small-scale mud crab fishers to exploitation. Participants described these as “rules made far away but felt every day,” reflecting the gap between policy and on-ground realities in the Sundarbans.

Boat License Certificates (BLCs) and exclusion

Central to the discussion was the Boat License Certificate (BLC) system. Under the Sundarbans Tiger Reserve (STR) framework, fishers entering creeks for crab or fish collection must hold a valid BLC. Stakeholders explained that these permits were historically issued to specific “traditional” fishing castes and families and can only be inherited, not transferred (Ghosh, 2015). Consequently, a vast majority of forest-dependent fishers, well over a million, remain excluded, while only about 700 valid BLCs continue to operate.

Participants called this a “permit monopoly,” forcing non-BLC families to:

1. Rent licensed boats at high cost,
2. Work as a low-wage crew for permit holders, or
3. Enter illegally and risk fines, gear seizure, or arrest.

One fisher expressed the frustration vividly: “*They say we are trespassing in our own waters. My grandfather fished here, but I cannot unless I pay someone else.*” This exclusion has deepened social divides between BLC holders, often better-off, and the majority who remain unlicensed. The group also reflected that increasing restrictions often lead to higher illegal harvests, a dynamic captured through the Restriction–Harvest Trade-off Curve (Figure 5).

Figure 5

*Restriction - harvest trade-off curve****Weak enforcement and lawlessness***

Participants highlighted the paradox of enforcement. While forest guards rigorously check BLC compliance, they do little to protect fishers from piracy and extortion. “The forest police chase us for permits, but no one could stop the hijackers,” complained one collector. Incidents of armed robbery during fishing trips, where boats are looted mid-river, were widely reported, consistent with documented piracy in the delta. Such insecurity adds both economic losses and mental stress to already precarious livelihoods.

Limited representation in policy processes

Stakeholders noted a near-total absence of fisher voices in decision-making. No active co-management forums exist within the Sundarbans Tiger Reserve or adjacent fishing zones, and official planning meetings rarely include small-scale fishers. As one trader stated, “Rules come to us on paper; nobody asks what will happen to our lives.” Even progressive frameworks such as the Forest Rights Act (2006), which can recognise community fishing rights, remain underused due to bureaucratic hurdles and low awareness in remote areas.

Market and extension gaps

Institutional shortcomings also extend to market and extension services. Fishers reported no government-supported infrastructure for cold storage, price dissemination, or cooperative development. In the absence of formal producer collectives, they negotiate prices individually and navigate subsidy schemes without organised support, leaving them Odisha, the Sundarbans crab fishery remains uncertified, preventing access to premium export markets. “Our crabs vulnerable to manipulation and inefficiency.

Certification and market access

The lack of eco-certification further restricts income opportunities. Unlike the MSC-certified Chilika Lake crab fishery in go to Kolkata, then maybe abroad, but we get less benefit from global prices,” a trader remarked. This reflects not only ecological management gaps but also institutional weaknesses in traceability and governance needed for certification.

d) Social drivers of vulnerability

The fourth major theme from the workshop concerned social challenges that compound economic and environmental pressures on small-scale mud crab fishers. Participants described these vulnerabilities as “the burdens we carry even when the nets are full,” showing how poverty, social exclusion, and health risks shape daily life.

Gender inequity and invisible labour

Women play a critical but undervalued role in the crab value chain, earning only ₹1,500–2,000 per month with little control over sales or pricing (Sahu et al., 2002). They have no formal role in decision-making and limited access to credit or savings, and many have lost their bank accounts due to floods or cyclones.

Marginalisation and caste-based exclusion

Scheduled caste and migrant fishing communities lack formal land or forest rights and face persistent discrimination in accessing permits, schemes, and relief measures.

Intergenerational disengagement

Younger generations are leaving the fishery for city jobs. “Our sons want city jobs. They see no future in crabs,” noted one elder, leading to loss of traditional knowledge and weakening community cohesion.

Social service gaps and hidden threats

Basic services are largely absent, including health clinics, schooling, and cyclone shelters. Health shocks reduce work capacity and force families into debt, with some travelling through multiple rivers to reach hospitals in emergencies.

Despite multiple vulnerabilities, the workshop highlighted pockets of viability that help sustain livelihoods for thousands of households in the Sundarbans mud crab fishery. Participants referred to these as the “reasons we can still stay and fish,” encompassing ecological, economic, institutional, and social factors.

a) Ecological drivers of viability

Sundarbans' estuarine and mangrove ecosystems remain crucial for mud crab production. High tidal exchange brings nutrient-rich waters, and creeks provide breeding and nursery grounds. "The tides feed our crabs," said one collector, highlighting the importance of daily flushing. *Scylla* species' tolerance to salinity fluctuations ensures they persist even as other fish disappear: "Other fish are gone, but the crabs stay with the salt." This ecological resilience underpins continued crab availability despite climate and hydrological changes.

b) Economic drivers of viability

Robust domestic and export demand, especially from Kolkata, Southeast Asia, and China, keeps prices attractive. Traders noted, "Kolkata buyers come even after a cyclone if we have crabs." Local market networks and informal crab fattening practices create steady income streams, particularly for export-grade large males and berried females.

c) Institutional drivers of viability

Although BLCs are often inequitable, they regulate access and prevent open-access overexploitation. Licensed fishers acknowledged, "Without BLC, anyone could enter and finish all the crabs." Informal norms within fishing hamlets guide gear sharing, conflict resolution, and rotational creek use. NGOs and women's groups provide entry points for dialogue, capacity-building, and alternative livelihoods, while training programs on crab fattening and market information offer modest but meaningful support.

d) Social drivers of viability

Traditional knowledge of tides, lunar cycles, and crab behaviour remains central to harvesting efficiency. "We know the moon tells when crabs are full," noted one senior collector. Women's vital role in sorting, cleaning, and marketing ensures household cash flow even when men are at sea. Low fishing costs, modest daily incomes, and collective efforts through shared boats and gear reduce operational risks and provide resilience against shocks.

5. Co-produced solutions

After examining key drivers and enablers, participants identified practical solutions to safeguard the crab fishery.

a) Ecological, harvest management & habitat protection

- ✓ Spawning-specific bans during peak spawning, based on fishers' knowledge.
- ✓ Seasonal mapping to align low market-demand months with larval rearing, ensuring the complete crab life cycle.
- ✓ Minimum legal size and catch quotas (≥ 80 g male, ≥ 60 g female) with daily limits and fair price support.
- ✓ Discouragement of fine-mesh gears (Charpatta jal, Behundi jal) in key breeding grounds.
- ✓ Community monitoring with monthly rotation of "resource watchers" receiving small remuneration.
- ✓ Control of point-source discharges from shrimp ponds and small industries.

- ✓ Community-led mangrove planting with multipurpose species such as Keora.
- ✓ Women-led village waste management initiatives focusing on drainage upkeep and plastic removal.

b) Alternative & supplementary livelihoods

- ✓ Expansion of mud crab aquaculture and fattening pilot projects (ICAR-CIFRI, RGCA, PMMSY), engaging collectors as labourers with assured wages.
- ✓ Integrated farming systems like raised-bed vegetables, rice–fish, or shrimp–crab culture.
- ✓ Women-led enterprises, including crab processing, handicrafts, and homestays/ecotourism.
- ✓ Skill-based supplementary jobs such as boat repair, vending, and tailoring, supported by microcredit.

c) Market & value chain improvements

- ✓ Collectors' cooperatives for bulk selling, collective transport, and cooperative pond farming.
- ✓ Mobile market information via phones or WhatsApp to track daily prices.
- ✓ Community cold storage and ice plants to prevent distress sales.
- ✓ Certified “Sundarbans Crab” brand for premium markets based on sustainability and traceability.
- ✓ Adoption of “Soft shell crab” technology from Bangladesh.

d) Governance & rights

- ✓ Co-management councils like the Sundarbans Fishers' Council for rule-setting and conflict resolution.
- ✓ Boat License Certificate reforms with gradual expansion to include women and trained new entrants.
- ✓ Community fishing zones, exploring legal recognition under the Forest Rights Act.

e) Capacity-building & safety

- ✓ Distribution of safety gear: life jackets, first-aid kits, and GPS devices.
- ✓ Environmental education campaigns on breeding cycles, waste management, and mangrove importance.

6. Collaborative implementation and monitoring for the mud crab fishery

To translate these solutions into action, roles and responsibilities were distributed among stakeholders. The participatory process ensured that solutions were linked to who can realistically lead, who benefits, and how equity is maintained. Practical monitoring indicators were also developed, grounded in what communities, officials, and researchers agreed are measurable and achievable.

Figure 6

Stakeholder responsibilities for sustainable mud crab management

Figure 6 suggests that stakeholders assume distinct roles to support the equitable and effective implementation of local solutions. Fishers and community groups could lead mangrove restoration, co-manage permits, and operate collective marketing, ensuring access, better prices, and resilience while prioritising the poorest households. Women's groups might run processing hubs and manage market linkages, promoting stable incomes and empowerment through reserved participation and training support. Forest and Fisheries Departments are encouraged to coordinate conservation and reform policies and support co-management, thereby enhancing legitimacy and reducing conflict through joint accountability. Local governments could invest in infrastructure, social protection, and pilot scaling, ensuring economic stability and transparent resource allocation. Traders and exporters may adopt fair procurement and traceability measures to stabilise supply chains and share premiums. NGOs are encouraged to facilitate capacity-building, legal aid, and inclusion-focused outreach for marginal households. Donors can provide funding, technical support, and risk-sharing to enable scalable outcomes with equity safeguards. At the same time, researchers are encouraged to support participatory evaluation, synthesise evidence, and translate findings into policy, following ethical and transparent practices. To track progress and ensure accountability, the following monitoring indicators were developed, as shown in Table 1.

Indicator	Purpose	Frequency	Data source	Suggested target
Catch per unit effort (CPUE) for mud crab	Tracks biological productivity and short-term fishery response	Monthly	Catch logs from fishers, landing site surveys	+15% CPUE within 24 months in intervention sites
Share of final retail price received by primary fishers (%)	Measures value capture and market equity	Biannual	Market surveys, trade records,	Increase fisher share by 20% within 12

			household surveys	months of collective marketing pilot
Area of mangrove replanted (ha) and 12-month survival rate (%)	Assesses ecosystem restoration progress and durability	Annual	Project records, satellite verification, field transects	100 ha replanted: 70% survival at 12 months (site-specific)
Number of households with community BLC or secure access arrangement	Tracks tenure/security outcomes from BLC reform pilots	Annual	Local registry, Panchayat records	60–80% of eligible households covered in pilot villages
Number and average income of women-led processing enterprises	Economic empowerment metric for post-harvest interventions	Annual	Enterprise surveys, bank records	Establish 3–5 enterprises; average income rise $\geq 30\%$ yr-on-yr
Incidence of post-harvest loss (%)	Measures improvements in cold storage, transport and value chain efficiency	Quarterly (peak season)	Landing Site Surveys, trader logs	Reduce loss by 30% in pilot sites within 12 months
Number of households covered by social protection / insurance payouts after shock	Social safety net effectiveness	Event-based + annual summary	Administrative records, household follow-up	80% of registered eligible households receive timely support after shocks
Number of operational pilot interventions (collective marketing, cold storage, restoration sites)	Implementation tracking	Quarterly	Project monitoring reports	3–5 pilots operational in first 12 months
Time to grievance resolution (days)	Governance and accountability measure	Quarterly	Grievance mechanism logs	Average resolution <30 days for registered complaints

7. Executive summary

The small-scale crab fisheries in the Indian Sundarbans are vital for the livelihoods of many coastal and estuarine households. The crab fishery generates significant revenue, especially for landless and marginal fishers, and is essential for sustaining the socio-ecological equilibrium of the delta. Fisheries are increasingly vulnerable to various environmental, socio-economic, and institutional challenges. Recurrent cyclones, habitat degradation, salinity intrusion, and market dependency have heightened livelihood insecurity, while restricted forest access and weak institutional linkages further constrain adaptive capacity.

This working paper analyses the co-production of knowledge and action, highlighting the active participation of fishers, scientists, local institutions, and policymakers in converting vulnerability into viability and resilience. This study employs participatory fieldwork and stakeholder dialogues in specific fishing villages to identify the dimensions of vulnerability affecting crab fishers and to examine potential pathways for improving resilience, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7

Conceptualisation of the abstract

The co-production process enabled local communities to articulate their knowledge of crab breeding cycles, tidal ecology, and traditional harvesting practices, leading to innovative local solutions such as community-based crab pens, participatory stock monitoring, and collective marketing initiatives. The growing participation of women in crab fattening and value addition represents a crucial element of livelihood diversification and empowerment.

The study highlights that sustainable viability depends on three interrelated pathways:

- ✓ Restoration and adaptive management of mangrove and estuarine ecosystems are critical for maintaining ecological balance and enhancing biodiversity.
- ✓ Frameworks for institutional enhancement and co-management are crucial to ensure equitable resource access and representation for fishers.
- ✓ Diversifying livelihoods and enhancing value chains are crucial steps towards reducing economic vulnerability.

Policy recommendations involve improving coordination between fisheries and forest departments, promoting inclusive co-management models, developing capacity-building programmes, and integrating small-scale crab fisheries into broader blue economy and climate adaptation frameworks. This paper examines co-production as both a process and an outcome, contributing to the global Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) initiative and offering replicable insights for small-scale fisheries in deltaic and climate-sensitive ecosystems.

8. Conclusions

The workshop identified a clear trajectory of outcomes for the mud crab fishery, spanning short, medium, and long-term horizons. In the short term (0–12 months), fishers are expected to gain a larger share of prices, operational pilots for cold storage and collective marketing will be established, and baseline monitoring systems put in place. Over the medium term (1–3 years), formalised community access arrangements, reduced post-harvest losses, and measurable increases in CPUE and women’s enterprise incomes are anticipated. Long-term goals (3–7 years) include landscape-level reductions in shrimp pond expansion, improved mangrove cover and ecosystem resilience, and the institutionalisation of co-management with equitable market linkages. All sequencing of interventions is guided by the “no one worse off” principle, ensuring equity safeguards and pilot evidence informs decisions. While the workshop produced actionable priorities, limitations remain: the outputs reflect only participating stakeholders; ecological interventions require site-level trials and long-term monitoring; medium- and large-scale interventions require detailed economic appraisal; and institutional reforms, such as BLC revisions, require legal and political feasibility studies.

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Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) Global Partnership

The Vulnerability to Viability (V2V) project is a transdisciplinary global partnership and knowledge network. Our aim is to support the transition of small-scale fisheries (SSF) from vulnerability to viability in Africa and Asia. Vulnerability is understood as a function of exposure, sensitivity and the capacity to respond to diverse drivers of change. We use the term viability not just in its economic sense but also to include its social, political, and ecological dimensions.

The V2V partnership brings together approximately 150 people and 70 organizations across six countries in Asia (Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Japan, Malaysia, Thailand), six countries in Africa (Ghana, Malawi, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania), Canada and globally. This unique initiative is characterized by diverse cultural and disciplinary perspectives, extensive capacity building and graduate student training activities, and grounded case studies from two regions of the world to show how and when SSF communities can proactively respond to challenges and creatively engage in solutions that build their viability. Further information on the V2V Partnership is available here: www.v2vglobalpartnership.org.

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